

The Logistics Performance in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "logistics performance" in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures how effectively a country manages the movement of goods and services within its borders and internationally. This variable assesses the capacity of a country's logistics infrastructure to support trade and industry, which is crucial for global competitiveness and innovation. High logistics performance implies a well-developed transportation system, efficient management of goods flows, and strong customs infrastructure. These factors contribute to reducing delivery times, operational costs, and improving access to international markets. Countries with advanced logistics infrastructures, such as well-connected ports, roads, and rail networks, tend to foster a more dynamic economic environment and attract investments. In the GII, logistics performance is a key indicator of a country's ability to support innovation, as an efficient logistics system facilitates integration into global value chains and the adoption of new technologies. Countries with low logistics performance, on the other hand, may struggle to expand their trade and innovate, thus limiting their economic growth potential. The data refer to the period from 2013 to 2022.

Logistics Performance in 2022. The data on logistics performance for 2022 show a stark disparity between countries, with the more developed nations leading the rankings, while many developing or fragile economies show relatively low results. Logistics performance is a crucial variable for a country's economic competitiveness, as it concerns the ability to move goods and services efficiently, thus supporting trade and industry. Germany ranks first with a perfect score of 100, followed by Sweden (93), Belgium (92.6), Austria (92.1), and Japan (92.1). These countries have highly developed logistics infrastructures, advanced transportation networks, and efficient management of commercial flows. Germany, in particular, is globally recognized for its excellence in transport infrastructure, from seaports to railway systems, enabling smooth and fast goods exchange both nationally and internationally. Netherlands (91.6) and Singapore (90.7), known for their large ports and strategic position in global trade, also maintain high levels of logistics performance. Their ability to quickly connect global trade networks is crucial to their economy. Similarly, United Arab Emirates (88.8) and Hong Kong (87) benefit from strong logistics infrastructures that facilitate international trade, making these economies key hubs for goods transshipment. Some developed countries, such as the United States (85.6), New Zealand (85.1), and France (83.3), also show solid logistics performance. However, these countries do not top the rankings, possibly due to geographical complexity or infrastructures that, while advanced, may not always compete with the global leaders. Italy (78.6), despite an extensive road and rail network, ranks slightly lower, perhaps due to inefficiencies in logistics management and ports, limiting its ability to further improve. An interesting point of reflection concerns countries like China (72.6) and South Korea (72.6), which have emerged as important global logistics hubs due to massive infrastructure investments. However, China, despite being an economic powerhouse, ranks significantly lower than leading European countries, suggesting there is still room for improvement in optimizing its vast logistics network. In emerging markets, countries like Vietnam (56.7) and India (52.6) are rapidly growing in logistics capacity, in line with their expanding economies. However, they face challenges related to outdated

infrastructures and the need for greater technological integration. The lower end of the rankings includes countries with severe infrastructural deficiencies and often political instability. Zimbabwe (3.3), Niger (0.9), and Burundi (0.5) record the lowest scores. These countries are characterized by weak logistics systems, lack of infrastructure investment, and difficulties in ensuring the security and stability necessary to promote trade. Poor connectivity and inefficiency in resource management make it challenging to improve their logistics performance. There is a clear divide between developed and developing countries. Advanced European and Asian nations tend to dominate the rankings thanks to their modern and integrated infrastructure. In contrast, African countries and some Latin American countries show relatively low logistics performance, limiting their commercial potential. Nations at the lower end of the rankings could benefit from significant infrastructure and technology investments, as well as economic policies aimed at improving supply chain management. Such improvements would allow for greater integration into global markets and stimulate long-term economic growth.

Logistics Performance Between 2013 and 2022. The data on logistics performance between 2013 and 2022 reveal notable changes, both positive and negative, for various countries worldwide. These changes highlight the impact of infrastructure investment, economic development, political stability, and technological integration, which are key factors in determining the effectiveness of a country's logistics system. Czechia, New Zealand, Germany, and Sweden registered among the most significant improvements in logistics performance. Czechia saw an absolute increase of 22.3 points (41.7%), suggesting that the country has invested significantly in its logistics infrastructure. This is consistent with Czechia's growing role as a manufacturing and logistics hub in Central Europe, where its proximity to large markets like Germany is a key factor. New Zealand, with an improvement of 40.7%, made notable strides, likely due to investments in transportation networks and efficient management of imports and exports, which are crucial for a geographically isolated country. Germany, already a global logistics leader, further improved its position, increasing its logistics performance by 31.9%. This reflects the country's continued focus on maintaining top-tier logistics infrastructures and technological innovation applied to supply chain management. Sweden, Austria, and Japan also saw significant improvements, with increases between 25% and 30%, consolidating their position as advanced countries in terms of logistics efficiency. Many countries, such as the United Kingdom, Belgium, France, and the United States, showed moderate growth, ranging from 16% to 25%. These countries, with advanced economies and already well-developed infrastructures, continued to invest in modernizing their logistics systems, but with a smaller margin for improvement compared to emerging or fast-growing countries. Spain, with a 22.7% increase, made progress, supported by investments in transportation infrastructure and efficient management of international logistics. Italy, with a 17.7% growth, improved its logistics infrastructure but likely still faces challenges related to bureaucratic inefficiencies and technological modernization. Several countries experienced a decline or stagnation in their logistics performance. India saw marginal improvement (+1.2%), while other countries, such as Iran, Romania, and Kenya, recorded slight decreases. In these cases, the absence of significant infrastructure investments, political instability, or lack of technological integration may have hindered progress.

Conclusion. Logistics performance decreased on average by 8.95% between 2013 and 2022. The top performers include Czechia with +41.70%, New Zealand with +40.70%, Rwanda with +34.60%, Germany with +31.90%, and Sweden with +30.40%. The worst performers were Senegal (-75.10%), Yemen (-78.40%), Guinea (-81.10%), Zimbabwe (-91.50%), and Niger (-97.9%).

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Appendix

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Czechia	53,5	75,8	22,3	41,7
	New Zealand	60,5	85,1	24,6	40,7
	Rwanda	31,8	42,8	11	34,6
	Germany	75,8	100	24,2	31,9
	Sweden	71,3	93	21,7	30,4
Worse Performance	Senegal	37,3	9,3	-28	-75,1
	Yemen, Rep.	47,3	10,2	-37,1	-78,4
	Guinea	37	7	-30	-81,1
	Zimbabwe	38,8	3,3	-35,5	-91,5
	Niger	42,3	0,9	-41,4	-97,9

